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Document History

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V0.2	14/02/2024	Deliverable content for reported activities by partners
V0.3	29/02/2024	Deliverable formatting and internal review
V1	29/02/2024	Final

¹ **Type:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action):

- R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** Use one of the following codes (in consistence with the Description of the Action)

- PU: Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN: Sensitive, limited under conditions of the Grant Agreement

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List of Abbreviations and definitions

The abbreviations and definitions used in the deliverable are based on the AIDAVA Glossary³.

³ <https://www.aidava.eu/helpdesk/glossary>

Executive Summary

The Report on dissemination and communication activities is part of WP6 “Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Sustainability”. The purpose of this WP is to foster outreach and engage various stakeholders through external communication of AIDAVA activities, progress and achievements, as well as dedicated disseminating activities and exploitation of potential results.

The current deliverable presents the dissemination and communication activities undertaken by members of the consortium for the period M01-M18. These activities are performed in accordance with the guidelines and framework described in *D6.2 Plan for Dissemination & exploitation of Results incl. Communication Activities (PDEC)*. An update to the PDEC in the form of *D6.6 Update of the PDEC in official report 1* provides more information about the activities planned to be performed past M18. These further dissemination and communication activities will be reported in *D6.10 Update of Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities 1* (due M36) and *D6.11 Update of Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities 2* (due M48).

1 Introduction

The integration of AI technologies in healthcare presents a pioneering opportunity to revolutionise patient data management. Recognizing this potential, our consortium initiated a project to develop an AI-based data curation virtual assistant to assist patients in navigating and curating their health data, thereby promoting a more patient-centric approach to healthcare. The project reflects a concerted effort to leverage technology for enhancing patient autonomy and engagement in the healthcare domain.

This report documents activities related to the dissemination and communication activities during 18 months of work of the AIDAVA project, around the technical achievements, stakeholder engagement strategies, and future directions of this initiative.

Key Achievements

- **Prototype Development:** Successful design and architecture of the prototype and the evaluation process through a formal study research protocol; successful development of the frontend of the prototype (wireframes) ongoing development of the different components of the backend of the prototype
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Established a broad network of support and collaboration across the healthcare ecosystem.
- **Knowledge Dissemination:** Significant impact achieved through various dissemination activities, raising awareness and understanding of the project's objectives and outcomes.

Throughout the project, the consortium navigated various challenges including technical hurdles, ethical considerations, and navigating the complex regulatory landscape. Key lessons learned include the importance of ongoing stakeholder engagement and the need for flexibility in project planning to adapt to unforeseen circumstances.

The development of an AI-based data curation virtual assistant marks a significant step forward in promoting patient-centric healthcare. Through the dedication and collaboration of the consortium, this project has laid the groundwork for empowering patients with the tools and knowledge needed to navigate their health data. The path ahead is filled with opportunities to expand upon this foundation, driving forward the agenda of patient empowerment and engagement in the healthcare landscape.

Following the introductory parts in Section 1, the rest of the document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the activities performed by the consortium during M1-M18. The section is composed of three parts. The first discusses the multipurpose tools and materials created by the consortium for the purposes of the AIDAVA project. The second part is a report on dissemination activities including scientific publications, participation in scientific events, clustering activities, and more. The last part presents the project's communication activities at digital and physical platforms, in the form of publicising the project on social networks and at various networking events, respectively. Finally, Appendix 1 provides a complete list of the consortium's communication activities on social media networks.

2 Description of Activities performed during M1-M18

A project's outreach can be broadly divided into two categories - spreading awareness about the project, its objectives and results, known as communication, and demonstrating and translating these results, known as dissemination. Various types of activities fall predominantly into one of those categories, however, some activities address both at the same time. We examine such multipurpose activities first, followed by a report on dissemination activities and a report on communication activities.

2.1 Multipurpose tools and materials

2.1.1 Project website

The first multipurpose tool that we examine is the AIDAVA project's website (<https://aidava.eu/>), which has previously been described in the D6.1 Public Project Website. The website contains a homepage and 6 further sections - About, Research, Impact, Resources, News & Events, and a Helpdesk.

Figure 1 AIDAVA project website

In the period since the website was first introduced the About section was expanded with an additional subsection for the project's "Meet the Partners"⁴ campaign. The campaign is a series of interviews on the project's website with members of the partner institutions. As of February 2024, the campaign has featured 3 members of NEMC and Averbis with further interviews planned for release in the upcoming months. Such interviews allow engaged stakeholders to get to know the people behind AIDAVA and what drives their involvement in the project.

⁴ <https://aidava.eu/about/interview>

Stefan Schulz

Institution/Lab
Averbis GmbH

Major Fields of Research/Activity
NLP, medical terminology

Share this Interview
aidava.eu/about/interview#stefan-schulz

What is your role in the AIDAVA team at INSTITUTION?

I am the Task Leader for Task 5.1, Novel DL/NLP tools for text-based content.

What are you currently working on within the scope of AIDAVA and what are your main goals and objectives in the project?

As a specialist in clinical language analysis, terminologies and ontologies I am leading Task 5.1 together with Kris Collins, and I am particularly tasked with the inclusion of the Averbis tools into the text annotation AIDAV workflow in terms of pre-annotation.

This requires a tight interaction with task 4.3, led by Medical University of Graz (MUG) where I hold a professorship in medical informatics.

Bridging these two activities, I am the main author of an annotation guideline used for the annotation of clinical narratives. On the part of MUG I am also the curator of the German Interface Terminology for SNOMED CT, which is used for the pre-annotation of clinical narratives in AIDAVA.

Why do you think, the AIDAVA research is important/will make a difference?

AI-readiness and language-independent reusability of clinical data, supported by standards like SNOMED CT and FHIR as the basis of a canonical, knowledge graph based canonic representation of a lifelong personal health record.

What motivates you, personally?

I am personally motivated in demonstrating the usefulness and feasibility of semantic standards, together with new NLP paradigms for interoperable health data, both for primary and secondary health data interoperability use cases.

Fun/personal fact

One of my favorite things to do when not doing research is reading, hiking, cycling, and playing the piano. One thing I cannot live without is reading and keeping myself informed about the world in all its aspects.

Figure 2 An interview with Stefan Schulz (AVERBIS), part of the "Meet the Partner" campaign

Another part of the website where new content has been added is the Resources⁵ section, which contains the periodic flash updates addressed to various stakeholders. So far 3 such updates have been published in November 2022 (M3)⁶, March 2023 (M7)⁷ and September 2023 (M13)⁸. Each periodic flash contains information about the project, its current status and next steps.

AIDAVA Flash Communication / September 2023

Contribution of Patient Consultants: First Year in Review

AIDAVA has successfully completed the first year of the project! During this time, the contribution of eight Patient Consultants from ECPC and EHN has been invaluable in ensuring that AIDAVA delivers a digital tool that makes sense for patients.

It has been a busy and productive year for them, with online meetings, a face-to-face workshop, documents to read and evaluate, questionnaires to complete, feedback to share...even other activities that were not originally planned. Let's take a look!

Patient's Contribution during this first year

At the end of 2022, eight Patient Consultants were invited to participate in an onboarding meeting to introduce AIDAVA, define their role in the project and identify the benefits that can incentivize patients to use such a tool. During 2023, they participated in several activities focused on ensuring that the system meets patients' needs: 1) definition of the use cases, 2) identification of personas and key features for users (e.g. level of health or digital literacy to identify a user rather than being a "patient" versus a "data expert"), 3) specification of business requirements, and 4) assessment of the patient-specific schedule of activities and documentation to be used during the evaluation of the system later in the project.

All of this work is serving as the basis for "building a data cleaning machine" that helps patients maintain a high-quality personal health record.

From September 2023, AIDAVA team will continue working with Patient Consultants on the evaluation and testing of the preliminary versions of the AIDAVA prototype - before it is tested by site patient in the summer of 2024. Exciting times ahead!

Next Steps

Thank you, Patient Consultants!

Figure 3 AIDAVA's 3rd periodic flash released in September 2023

⁵ <https://aidava.eu/library>

⁶ https://aidava.eu/library/AIDAVA_periodic-flash_Nov22.pdf

⁷ https://aidava.eu/library/AIDAVA_PeriodicFlash_March2023.pdf

⁸ https://aidava.eu/library/AIDAVA_PeriodicFlash_Sept2023.pdf

The last section, which has been regularly updated is News & Events, which the consortium regularly uses to announce past and upcoming events in which AIDAVA partners participate, as well as other updates about the project.

Figure 4 Recent news and events on AIDAVA's website

2.1.2 Project management platform

Successful execution of the project requires effective communication between consortium members with regard to common objectives, current progress and obtained results. Towards this purpose, EURICE is hosting an internal project management platform⁹, which only consortium members can access after authorisation. The platform hosts documents, tracks issues, and offers an interactive Gantt chart and agile project management tools. Each work package has a dedicated section where members can access package-specific information and track progress on the package's tasks and deliverables. In addition, separate sections for Communication, Dissemination and Publishing activities are also included, as such activities often span across multiple work packages.

⁹ <https://aidava.eurice.eu/>

Figure 5 AIDAVA's project management platform

2.1.3 Project identity - logo and templates

Integral to the project's dissemination and communication activities is a consistent and suitable project identity. The identity should reflect the project's essence, while ideally also standing out and being memorable. The project's identity was introduced in the D6.4 *AIDAVA Communication Toolkit*. The deliverable describes the project logo and colour scheme and presents AIDAVA-themed templates for presentations, posters, and deliverables, as well as a project slide deck to be used by all partners. All of these materials have been made available in the project's management platform, described in the previous subsection, and have been adopted consistently by the members of the consortium.

2.1.4 Marketing materials

In addition to the abovementioned templates and project slide deck, the project's identity is also communicated through various physical marketing materials, also introduced in the D6.4 *AIDAVA Communication Toolkit*. AIDAVA-branded tote bags, mouse pads, notepads, and pens were handed out to partners during the project's Kick-off meeting and have been made available to partners to distribute to key stakeholders at various scientific and networking events.

Figure 6 AIDAVA-themed marketing materials

2.1.5 Audio-visual materials

D6.5 *Audio-visual material* was produced by the consortium at M12. The audio-visual material generated is a short, animated video that introduces the project and its benefits to key stakeholders. The video¹⁰ has been made available on YouTube and has been shared by multiple partners via their social media channels, as is described in Section 2.3.1 *Social Networks* of the current deliverable. In addition, the video is intended to be used throughout the duration of the project at various venues where the project is to be communicated or disseminated. Only 3 months after its release the video has been viewed more than 320 times.

Figure 7 AIDAVA audio-video material.

¹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oRLB7iBDYnw>

2.1.6 Other multipurpose tools and materials

In addition to the abovementioned activities, individual consortium partners have been communicating the project through their digital channels. NEMC, EHN, ONTO, UM and GND all shared through their respective websites and newsletters announcements^{11,12} of the project's launch. Later on, partners continued using those channels to communicate updates and further information about AIDAVA. For example, before the launch of the "Meet the Partner" campaign described earlier in this deliverable, ONTO organised 2 interviews with the project's clinical and technical coordinators Isabelle de Zegher and Remzi Celebi. The interviews were published on ONTO's website as well as its newsletter, thus reaching long-term partners and clients of the company, as well as other parties interested in ONTO's activities.

2.2 Dissemination Activities Report

Dissemination activities are an integral part of the visibility and outreach of a project. The main objective of such activities is to publicise the project's achievements and promote its future development. The consortium has previously outlined 3 categories of dissemination activities in Section 5.3 *Planned dissemination activities* of the PDEC (D6.2). These are open-access scientific publications, clustering with other Horizon projects, and networking with stakeholders. The current deliverable examines the latter category in four parts - participation at scientific events, dissemination of deliverables, education and training events, and other dissemination events and meetings.

2.2.1 Scientific Publications

Publications in scientific journals and at conference proceedings are an essential part of the dissemination of the project's activities. Crucially, such publications should be open access in order to be freely available to the broader public and reach a wider target audience.

The publications plan in section 5.3 *Planned dissemination activities* of the PDEC (D6.2) lists 6 papers to be published by the end of the project which will disseminate key findings and innovations from the project. The planned publications are to cover the contributions by various work packages - one publication is to describe advances in WP1, another one covers WP2 & WP3, and one for WP4. The remaining 3 planned publications cover various aspects of WP5 - knowledge extraction from clinical texts, healthcare data quality enhancement, and explainable AI.

During the first 18 months of the project, the consortium has published 6 scientific articles and has submitted another 1, which is currently under review. Out of the 7 publications, 5 are in scientific journals, while the other 2 are in conference or workshop proceedings. Topics of the publications range from ontology-based annotations of clinical narratives to deep learning applications for breast cancer, to benchmarking AI algorithms.

A full list of the consortium's published scientific publications during the period M1-M18 is provided in the following table. The remaining publication, titled "Artificial Intelligence-based Data Curation:

¹¹

<https://www.regionaalhaigla.ee/en/new-eu-research-project-launches-automate-curation-and-publishing-personal-health-data-through>

¹² <https://egnosis.ro/research/aidava/>

enabling a Patient-Centric European Health Data Space", was submitted to the journal *Frontiers in Medicine*¹³ in January 2024 and is currently under review.

Table 1 List of publications for M1-M18

Status	Publication
Published	Beuque, Manon PL, Marc BI Lobbes, Yvanka van Wijk, Yousif Widaatalla, Sergey Primakov, Michael Majer, Corinne Balleyguier, Henry C. Woodruff, and Philippe Lambin. "Combining deep learning and handcrafted radiomics for classification of suspicious lesions on contrast-enhanced mammograms." <i>Radiology</i> 307, no. 5 (2023): e221843. PID: https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.221843
Published	Gu, Jionghui, Xian Zhong, Chengyu Fang, Wenjing Lou, Peifen Fu, Henry C. Woodruff, Baohua Wang, Tianan Jiang, and Philippe Lambin. "Deep Learning of Multimodal Ultrasound: Stratifying the Response to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy in Breast Cancer Before Treatment." <i>The Oncologist</i> 29, no. 2 (2024): e187-e197. PID: https://doi.org/10.1093/oncolo/oyad227
Published	Holzinger, Andreas, Katharina Keiblinger, Petr Holub, Kurt Zatloukal, and Heimo Müller. "AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligence for biotechnology." <i>New Biotechnology</i> 74 (2023): 16-24. PID: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2023.02.001
Published	Holzinger, Andreas, Anna Saranti, Alessa Angerschmid, Bettina Finzel, Ute Schmid, and Heimo Mueller. "Toward human-level concept learning: Pattern benchmarking for AI algorithms." <i>Patterns</i> (2023). PID: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2023.100788
Published	Mehryar, Shervin, and Remzi Celebi. "Semantic Annotation of Tabular Data for Machine-to-Machine Interoperability via Neuro-Symbolic Anchoring." In <i>CEUR Workshop Proceedings</i> , vol. 3557, pp. 61-71. Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen* Lehrstuhl Informatik V, 2023. PID: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3557/paper5.pdf
Published	Schulz, Stefan, Warren Del-Pinto, Lifeng Han, Markus Kreuzthaler, Sareh Aghaei, and Goran Nenadic. "Towards principles of ontology-based annotation of clinical narratives." In <i>Proceedings of the International Conference on Biomedical Ontologies</i> , vol. 2023. 2023. PID: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3603/Paper4.pdf

As of February 2024, four of the publications are indexed in Scopus - 2 articles, 1 conference paper and 1 review paper. Collectively, they've been cited a total of 66 times within Scopus-indexed articles (excluding self-citations). Out of these, 51 citations happened in 2023 with the remaining 14 during just the first two months of 2024.

Documents	Citations	<2020	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Subtotal	>2024	Total
	Total	0	0	0	0	51	15	66	1	67
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Toward human-level concept learning: Pattern benchmarking fo...	2023					2	2	4		4
<input type="checkbox"/> 2 Combining Deep Learning and Handcrafted Radiomics for Classi...	2023					5	1	6	1	7
<input type="checkbox"/> 3 AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligence for biotechno...	2023					44	12	56		56
<input type="checkbox"/> 4 Semantic Annotation of Tabular Data for Machine-to-Machine L...	2023							0		0

Display: 20 results per page 1 Top of page

Figure 8 Number of citations by publication within Scopus-indexed publications.

¹³ <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/medicine>

The paper *AI for Life: Trends in Artificial Intelligence for biotechnology* published in *New Biotechnology* is the most popular of the four indexed in Scopus, having been cited a total of 56 times. It provides an overview of open research issues and challenges across a wide range of topics from machine learning and Big Data analytics, knowledge discovery and data mining, biomedical ontologies, knowledge-based reasoning, natural language processing, decision support and reasoning under uncertainty, temporal and spatial representation and inference, and methodological aspects of explainable AI (XAI) with applications of biotechnology. *New Biotechnology*¹⁴ is an Elsevier journal which is ranked within the Q1 of journals for 3 ASJC categories - Biotechnology, Bioengineering, and Molecular Biology.

Among the consortium's publications is the paper titled *Combining Deep Learning and handcrafted radiomics for classification of Suspicious Lesions on contrast-enhanced Mammograms* published in the *Journal of Radiology* is not. The *Journal of Radiology* is ranked 1st among 312 journals according to the CiteScore¹⁵ journal ranking in the ASJC category for Radiology, Nuclear Medicine and Imaging.

Figure 9 CiteScore rank for journals containing AIDAVA publications

In total 3 of the 4 papers indexed in Scopus are also indexed in Web of Science (WoS)¹⁶. In addition, the paper "Deep Learning of Multimodal Ultrasound: Stratifying the Response to Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy in Breast Cancer Before Treatment." was published in September 2023 in *The Oncologist*¹⁷. WoS has recorded 48 citations of the 4 publications in 2023, none of which are self-citations.

Scopus and Web of Science both show a diverse range of topics covered by the AIDAVA publications indexed by them with 5 and 7 topics, respectively. Scopus defines topics more broadly, of which the following are covered: Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology, Chemical Engineering, Computer Science, Decision Sciences, and Medicine. WoS categories are more narrowly defined and the 7 covered by the AIDAVA-indexed publications are:

¹⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/new-biotechnology>

¹⁵ <https://www.scopus.com/sources>

¹⁶ <https://mjl.clarivate.com/home>

¹⁷ <https://academic.oup.com/oncolo/pages/about>

- Biochemical Research Methods
- Biotechnology Applied Microbiology
- Computer Science Artificial Intelligence
- Computer Science Information Systems
- Computer Science Interdisciplinary Applications
- Oncology
- Radiology Nuclear medicine Medical Imaging

Figure 10 Subject areas of AIDAVA papers indexed in Scopus

Figure 11 Topics covered by AIDAVA publications indexed WoS

Harzing's Publish or Perish¹⁸ offers yet another opportunity to track citations of publications. The software offers easy search within the full text of publications indexed on Google Scholar¹⁹. Google Scholar indexes a much broader range of publications compared to Scopus and WoS. Searching within the full text enables easy identification of all publications related to a project, by searching for the project's name (AIDAVA) or the project's ID (101057062), as those should be included in the Acknowledgements section of each project-related publication.

Search by the project's ID returns all 6 published publications (and one duplicate) with a total of 129 citations. Unlike Scopus and WoS, Harzing's Publish or Perish does not exclude self-citations, but the number of those is negligible given the total number of AIDAVA publications. Meanwhile, a search by the project's name returns over 20 results, indicating that the AIDAVA abbreviation is also used in other contexts within the scientific community and searching for the project by its ID is more reliable.

¹⁸ <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>

¹⁹ <https://scholar.google.com/>

Citation metrics		Help	
Publication years:	2023-2024		
Citation years:	1 (2023-2024)		
Papers:	7		
Citations:	129		
Cites/year:	129.00		
Cites/paper:	18.43		
Authors/paper:	4.57		
h-index:	3		
g-index:	7		

Cites	Per year	Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Publication	Publisher
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0	0.00	6	J Gu, X Zhong, C Fa...	Deep Learning of Multimodal Ultraso...	2024	The ...	academic.oup.com
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> h 112	112.00	1	A Holzinger, K Keib...	AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligen...	2023	New ...	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1	1.00	2	S Mehryar, R Celebi	Semantic Annotation of Tabular Data ...	2023	CEUR Workshop Proceedin...	ceur-ws.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> h 11	11.00	3	MPL Beuque, MBI L...	Combining deep learning and handcr...	2023	Radiology	pubs.rsna.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> h 4	4.00	4	A Holzinger, A Sara...	Toward human-level concept learning...	2023	Patterns	cell.com
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1	1.00	5	S Schulz, W Del-Pin...	Towards principles of ontology-base...	2023	Proceedings of the ...	researchgate.net
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 0	0.00	7	S Schulz, W Del-Pin...	Principles of ontology-based annotat...	2023		researchgate.net

Figure 12 AIDAVA publications on Harzing's Publish or Perish retrieved by project ID

While Scopus, WoS and Harzing's Publish or Perish track the number of citations in other publications, Altmetric²⁰ also monitors mentions of papers on news sources, blogs and social media platforms. The two most cited papers published by the AIDAVA consortium also stand out in terms of their propagation on such venues. The paper "Combining deep learning and handcrafted radiomics for classification of suspicious lesions on contrast-enhanced mammograms." has been mentioned by 2 news outlets²¹, 1 blog²² and mentioned in X (formerly Twitter) by 12 users. On the other hand, "AI for life: Trends in artificial intelligence for biotechnology." has been mentioned by 6 X users, 1 Facebook page, and has 339 readers on Mendeley²³.

²⁰ <https://www.altmetric.com>

²¹

<https://www.auntminnieeurope.com/imaging-informatics/artificial-intelligence/article/15657962/european-br-east-study-reports-positive-findings-on-ai-model>

²²

<https://www.auntminnie.com/clinical-news/womens-imaging/breast/article/15633678/deeplearning-model-performs-well-with-cem-images>

²³ <https://www.mendeley.com/>

Figure 13 AIDAVA scientific publications discussed on social media and other online platforms

Figure 14 Geographic coverage of interest to scientific publication

2.2.2 Participation in Scientific Events

The consortium has identified scientific conferences and symposia which are of relevance to the project in section 5.3 *Planned dissemination activities* of the PDEC (D6.2). The list includes recurring annual or biennial conferences targeted at hospitals, healthcare providers, health tech, and industry, as well as data stewards, regulators, policymakers, patients, and also various segments of the scientific community - from biomedicine to NLP, ML and Semantic technologies.

b!lo also gave a presentation at the Women in Data Science (WiDS) Maastricht²⁴ conference in March 2023. Active participation at such events benefits the project through dissemination to data scientists, data stewards and other technical roles working on Health Data.

Another event where b!lo presented the AIDAVA project is the annual conference organised by another consortium partner - the European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (IHD), which was themed "Building Trust in Health Data"²⁵ and held in November 2023. The conference focused on policy making and brought together over 300 people in person and online from key target audiences, among them EU Institutions, as well as National, Regional, and Local authorities.

Participation at other scientific events including the Cancer workshops organised by the EC and the European Electronic Health Record (EHR) Exchange Format Expert Summit²⁶, organised by the XpandH project²⁷ in collaboration with the European Commission, are further opportunities used by consortium members to connect and exchange ideas with stakeholders within the EU and beyond.

Overall, during the M1-M18 period, the consortium has maintained a regular and active presence at scientific events aimed at the various target groups identified in the PDEC (D6.2). These engagements are to continue throughout the remainder of the project and future plans can be found in D6.6 *Update of the PDEC in official report 1*.

Table 2 Attended conferences between M1 and M18

Dissemination activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
SemTab'23 workshop at the International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC)	Paper and poster presentations at the SemTab'23 workshop	business, startups, research communities	UM	Sep 2023
14 th International Conference on Biomedical Ontology (ICBO)	Paper presentation	business, startups, research communities	MUG	Oct 2023
annual MyData conference	Chair of Health & Ethics session	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities, civil society,	b!lo	May - June 2023
Woman in Data Sciences, Maastricht	Presentation	research communities, businesses, startups	UM, b!lo	March 2023
Cancer workshops organised by EC	Participation	business, public sector, regulators, research communities	b!lo	Nov 2023

²⁴ <https://wids.nl/event/2023/women-in-data-science-maastricht-2023/>

²⁵ <https://www.i-hd.eu/ac2023/>

²⁶ <https://xpandh-project.iscte-iul.pt/xpandh-ehr-exchange-format-expert-summit/>

²⁷ <https://xpandh-project.iscte-iul.pt/>

Dissemination activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
EU Expert Summit on EEHRxF	Participation	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities	b!lo	Dec 2023
IHD annual conference	Presentation	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities	IHD, UM, b!lo	Nov 2023

2.2.3 Dissemination of deliverables

In order to foster the dissemination of the AIDAVA project, the consortium agreed to make project deliverables more easily accessible to a wider audience. Towards this goal, all deliverables with a *Public* dissemination level have been made openly available on Zenodo²⁸. Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository which allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artefacts. All materials shared on Zenodo are indexed via a DOI, which enables both easier citation and also tracking of citations. As of M18, the consortium has made available 11 *Public* deliverables, namely:

- *D1.1 Description of use cases*²⁹
- *D1.2 Report from user survey with personas canvas*³⁰
- *D1.3 Business requirements for G1*³¹
- *D1.4 Definition of assessment study including test scenarios & metrics, and study initiation package*³²
- *D2.1 Global Data Sharing Standard*³³
- *D2.3 Solution Design Document for G1*³⁴
- *D3.1 VA architecture (Application and Technical)*³⁵
- *D4.1 Annotation guidelines*³⁶
- *D4.2 Data Management Plan (DMP)*³⁷
- *D4.3 Update to Annotation guidelines, tools & training*³⁸
- *D4.4 Information Governance Framework and Instruments*³⁹

These deliverables cover a wide range of aspects of the project. This enables various stakeholders to become aware of and familiar with the project, whether they are more interested in the data management and information governance, the solution design and architecture, the use cases and

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org>

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10075524>

³⁰ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10593216>

³¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10075579>

³² <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10245663>

³³ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10117717>

³⁴ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10245772>

³⁵ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10593464>

³⁶ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10593536>

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10075332>

³⁸ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10593799>

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10650564>

personas, or the business requirements and assessment metrics. For each deliverable made available on Zenodo we provide the number of views and downloads via that platform in the figure below.

Dissemination of Deliverables - Zenodo

Figure 15 Number of views and downloads on Zenodo by deliverable

Zenodo was developed under the European OpenAIRE program. Consequently, materials uploaded on Zenodo are also made available on the OpenAIRE platform, which further boosts the visibility of the project and its publicly shared deliverables. Below we include a few examples of AIDAVA deliverables indexed on the OpenAIRE platform.

Figure 16 AIDAVA deliverables indexed on the OpenAIRE platform

The consortium plans to continue uploading on Zenodo deliverables marked for *Public* dissemination throughout the project.

2.2.4 Clustering activities and collaboration with other EU-funded projects

Members of the consortium took part in various types of events aimed at fostering collaboration with other projects. For example, b!lo and ONTO both took part in the 2023 TEHDAS Stakeholder Forum⁴⁰ in order to gain insights on policies and best practices in the healthcare domain that are to be implemented towards the AIDAVA project. The TEHDAS project, part of the European Health Data Space (EHDS)⁴¹ initiative, was identified in the PDEC (D6.2) as a suitable venue for networking with major EU initiatives.

The PDEC also outlined the need to network with other projects within the “Innovative Tools for Electronic Health Records and Patient Registries” (InToEHR)⁴² cluster. Activities in this category include b!lo and UM's participation at an EU projects' roundtable “Privacy and technological scenarios on reuse of health data”⁴³ organised in June 2023 by the DataTools4Heart⁴⁴ project, as well as ONTO's contributions to the NLP group of the InToEHR cluster.

Figure 17 Isabelle de Zegher (b!lo) at the InToEHR cluster meeting, Brussels

The consortium engagement in collaboration activities ranges from acquiring valuable information and knowledge to also being an active provider of such. ONTO's participation in the European Health Data Space (EHDS)⁴⁵ was aimed at gaining insights into the global EU vision for health data. On the

⁴⁰ <https://tehdas.eu/event/tehdas-stakeholder-forum-2023/>

⁴¹ https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space_en

⁴²

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-hlt-h-2021-tool-06-03>

⁴³

<https://www.datatools4heart.eu/2023/05/24/health-data-reuse-an-overview-of-technological-and-legal-scenarios/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.datatools4heart.eu/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.european-health-data-space.com/>

other hand, ONTO's participation at the second stakeholder workshop⁴⁶ held by the HealthyCloud⁴⁷ project in December 2022 allowed the consortium to provide valuable feedback on recommendations for changes to health regulation.

Table 3 Clustering and collaboration activities between M1 and M18

Dissemination activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
Participation in the "Privacy & tech scenarios on reuse of health data" roundtable	EU projects' roundtable organised by Data4Heart project	innovators, EU institutions, research communities	b!lo	June 2023
InToEHR	provide feedback to the NLP group	innovators, EU institutions, research communities	ONTO	April 2023
Participation in TEHDAS Stakeholder Forum 2023	policies and Best Practices in Healthcare domain	innovators, EU institutions, national, regional & local authorities, research communities, international organisations	b!lo, ONTO, IHD	June 2023
HealthyCloud	feedback on recommendations for changes to health regulation	innovators, EU institutions, national, regional & local authorities, research communities	ONTO	Jan 2023
European Health Data Spaces (EHDS)	gain insights on the global EU vision for health data	innovators, EU institutions, national authorities, research communities	ONTO IHD b!lo	Oct 2023

2.2.5 Education and Training Events

During the first 18 months, separate members of the consortium have organised local, as well as global education and training events.

NEMC, for example, held a live recorded info session for all hospital group employees (about 5000 total) to introduce them to the AIDAVA project. Hospital staff is an integral part of the end user community and their engagement with the project early on can provide valuable feedback.

ONTO gave an introductory webinar on Knowledge graphs to the consortium, which was later adapted for broader communication and was also made publicly available on AIDAVA's YouTube account. We elaborate on the video's outreach on Youtube in section 2.3.1 *Social Networks* of this deliverable)

⁴⁶

<https://healthycloud.eu/event/stakeholder-forum-with-technical-users-of-the-future-health-research-and-innovation-cloud-duplicate-1/>

⁴⁷ HealthyCloud is a H2020 project with the objective to deliver a strategic agenda for the European Health Research and Innovation Cloud's ecosystem <https://healthycloud.eu/>

Table 4 Education and training events between M1 and M18

Dissem. activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
Introduction to AIDAVA project at live recorded info session	Introduce hospital staff to AIDAVA	ca 5000 hospital group employees	NEMC	Oct 2022
Webinar on Knowledge Graphs	Introductory webinar on Knowledge Graphs	innovators, research communities	ONTO	Feb 2023
Educational cooperation with Sofia University	exchange of know-how on knowledge engineering and NLP for biomedicine and healthcare	research communities	ONTO	Ongoing

2.2.6 Other dissemination events and meetings

In addition to the abovementioned activities, members of the consortium have organised or participated in various other events and meetings. NEMC held a meeting with a delegation from New Zealand including representatives from Te Whatu Ora/Health NZ and the University of Auckland National Institute for Health Innovation and gave a presentation about the project. Similarly, ONTO hosted a meeting with a HADEA delegation, in which the two parties discussed EC projects in which ONTO participates.

Figure 18 Ontotext representatives with members of the HADEA delegation - September 2023, Sofia, Bulgaria

NEMC has additionally boosted the visibility of the project to the research community by registering their involvement with AIDAVA at the Estonian Research Information System (ETIS)^{48,49}. The ETIS portal provides general information about the project, relevant fields and speciality, as well as details on the funding and staff of Estonian institutions involved.

⁴⁸ Estonian Research Information System (ETIS) portal: <https://www.etis.ee/>

⁴⁹ AIDAVA on ETIS portal <https://www.etis.ee/Portal/Projects/Display/aec5f93b-97fb-4895-9607-c06e4bfb92c1>

Figure 19 AIDAVA project on the ETIS platform

2.3 Communication Activities Report

Effective communication plays a key role in the success of any Horizon project. The PDEC (D6.2) identified 10 target groups for communication activities shown in the following figure:

The PDEC also outlines various external communication channels through which these target groups are to be engaged, as shown in the figure below.

A challenge faced in the beginning phase of the project was that there were no immediate results available which could be communicated. The solution adopted by the consortium is to direct early communication on promoting the project itself, explaining key features, as well as sharing envisaged activities and desired outcomes. These activities are undertaken in line with section 8.1 *Overall Communication Strategy and Management* of the PDEC (D6.2).

From the onset of the AIDAVA project, the consortium's Communications Committee has held regular meetings to iteratively plan, execute and monitor a consistent communication strategy. During the first 6 months these meetings were held twice a month, afterwards the regularity was set to once a month. This approach allows the consortium to adapt its messaging as new opportunities for communication become available, but also to proactively create such new opportunities. Some notable outcomes of this iterative process include:

- adapting recordings of internal webinars for external communication. The first of these has already been made available on the project's Youtube page with more recordings processed and scheduled to be uploaded during the next period.
- Creating the Meet the Partner campaign with interviews on the project's website and communicating these interviews via the project's social media channels, specifically LinkedIn and X.
- Uploading the project's public deliverables on Zenodo, to enhance their visibility and enable easier spread and citing of the deliverables via a persistent identifier (PID).

2.3.1 Social Media Networks

Social networks of relevance to the AIDAVA project were identified at the beginning of the project and accounts specific to the project were created on the following platforms:

- X (formerly known as Twitter)⁵⁰
- LinkedIn⁵¹
- Youtube⁵²
- ResearchGate⁵³

Activity on X

AIDAVA maintains an active presence on X and LinkedIn by sharing information about the project and its participants, as well as by reposting relevant activities by the consortium members.

Figure 20 AIDAVA's profile on X

⁵⁰ https://twitter.com/aidava_project

⁵¹ <https://be.linkedin.com/showcase/aidava-project/>

⁵² <https://www.youtube.com/@aidavaproject>

⁵³ <https://www.researchgate.net/project/AIDAVA-AI-powered-Data-Curation-Publishing-Virtual-Assistant>
(discontinued on March 31, 2023)

X is the social network where members of the consortium are most active and also where posts about AIDAVA have gained the greatest audience. During the M1-M18 period, the AIDAVA X profile has gained 39 followers, published 16 and retweeted 27 posts. The 16 posts published directly by the AIDAVA project account have received 109 reactions and over 2995 impressions. Of the 27 retweets, 23 were of AIDAVA-related posts by consortium members and the remaining 4 were related to various events and initiatives in which the project participated.

A significant part of AIDAVA's reach on X has been achieved by active promotion of the project via established accounts by members of the consortium. Partners of the consortium who have been most active in sharing content related to AIDAVA are ONTO, MUG (through *The Augmented Pathologist* profile), EHN, and ECPC. A summary of their respective AIDAVA-related activities on the platform, along with the activity by the AIDAVA project account, is provided in the figure below.

Figure 21 Number of posts, followers, reactions and impressions on X by consortium partner

The consortium has adopted the use of hashtags #AIDAVA and #aidava_project. The first has been used a total of 9 times, while the latter - 5. As hashtags are free to be used by all users of the X platform, the consortium has no control over what other posts are shared by other users using the #AIDAVA and #aidava_project hashtags. This can potentially create ambiguity about the meaning of AIDAVA, however, as of February 2024, both hashtags have rarely been used by other users for purposes not related to the project.

Example posts by the consortium are shown in the figure below. All posts by consortium members on the X platform are included in Appendix 3 List of communication activities of the current deliverable.

Figure 22 Sample posts by the AIDAVA consortium on X

Activity on LinkedIn

The AIDAVA LinkedIn profile has 126 followers as of February 2024. The account is regularly used to publish updates about the project, as well as to repost relevant content by consortium members, as well as project stakeholders. All LinkedIn posts related to the project can be found in Appendix 3 *List of communication activities* of the current deliverable.

Figure 23 AIDAVA profile on LinkedIn

To boost the project's visibility, the consortium organised the "Meet the Partners" campaign, described in Section 2.1 *Multipurpose tools and materials* of the current deliverable. To broaden the reach of the campaign, new interviews are publicised on the project's X and LinkedIn accounts. In a separate campaign ONTO shared on their LinkedIn account a couple of interviews with the project's Technical and Clinical Coordinators, which were reposted by the consortium's account.

Another type of regularly posted content is announcements and updates about workshops, general assemblies, as well as other gatherings of consortium members. The regular emphasis on such meetings demonstrates that members are engaged and actively cooperating among themselves towards reaching the project's objectives.

A third type of posts and reposts by the AIDAVA account contains information about the consortium's participation in various scientific, industry and other conferences and events. Active involvement in such events demonstrates that the project's activities are not performed in isolation, but rather are aligned with developments in relevant domains.

The AIDAVA LinkedIn profile also features opinions about the project expressed by domain experts not part of the consortium. This demonstrates the validation of the project by external parties.

Other content published on the AIDAVA LinkedIn profile includes publicising surveys aimed at end users, as well as content that demonstrates values and behaviours embraced by the consortium, such as celebrating the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

Figure 24 Examples of AIDAVA-related posts on LinkedIn

Activity on other social networks

The project's YouTube account has been used to share a recording of an introductory webinar on Knowledge Graphs⁵⁴. The topic was presented by ONTO to the other members of the consortium in February 2023. After minor adaptations and consent from the presenters, the video was uploaded on YouTube in order to reach a broader audience. As of February 2024, the webinar has been viewed 41 times on that platform.

⁵⁴ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vGyPiT_dzf4

Another video that the consortium shared on YouTube is the project's introductory video, described in Section 2.1 of the current deliverable. As of February 2024, the video has been viewed 298 times.

Lastly, GND has published a short video⁵⁵ on their YouTube channel containing coverage of a meeting of the consortium and interviews with multiple members of the consortium.

Figure 25 AIDAVA videos made available on Youtube

ResearchGate was chosen as a similar platform to X and LinkedIn but with more focus on the scientific community. Unfortunately, ResearchGate discontinued pages for research projects on 31st March 2023, thus efforts to promote the project were redistributed to the other social network platforms.

2.3.2 Participation in Various Events

During the first 18 months of the project members of the consortium successfully identified and participated in various events to communicate the project to the broader audience. ECPC, for example, gave a presentation at the Workshop on Landscaping data-driven projects and initiatives in the cancer field. The workshop was the first of 3 invitation-only online workshops organised by the European Commission. The attendees were consortium members of EU-funded data-driven cancer research projects and initiatives, making the event a great opportunity to establish future collaboration with stakeholders in the cancer field.

NEMC organised a Local Science and Innovation Conference at which the AIDAVA project was presented as a poster. This demonstrates the consortium's commitment to engage stakeholders not just globally, but also in a local setting.

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-ZmSZBVGAOU>

Former EHN's EU Project and Communication Officer, Isabella Cinà, gave a presentation at the EHN Annual Workshop 2023 on Patient involvement in EU-funded projects. The event was aimed at civil society and the research community.

ONTO took part in events aimed at a diverse range of target audiences. Among them was BioTechX 2023⁵⁶, which is Europe's largest pharmaceutical development and healthcare event. ONTO representatives hosted a talk part of the data integration track and had a booth to communicate the company's involvement and expertise in the domain⁵⁷.

Another notable event attended by ONTO was the Dataweek by BDVA, where the participants were able to attend and discuss with policymakers and representatives of other Big Data projects. This was followed a few months later by participation and involvement in discussions with policymakers and representatives of other projects at Infoday Horizon Europe 2023 in Sofia.

Participation in RANLP 2023 and ISWC 2023 enabled discussions with NLP and Semantic Technology experts respectively.

Table 5 Communication activities at events between M1 and M18

Commun. activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
Presentation to the first EC Workshop on Landscaping data driven projects and initiatives in the cancer field	explore synergies among different actions and contribute to a policy dialogue with the EC services	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities	ECPC	Oct 2023
AIDAVA poster at Local Science and Innovation Conference organised by NEMC	Communicate the AIDAVA project to researchers and innovators in the field	innovators, research communities, business, startups	NEMC	April 2023
Presentation at the EHN Annual Workshop 2023 Patient involvement in EU-funded projects: AIDAVA	Presentation by former EHN's EU Project and Communication Officer, Isabella Cinà, with participation by Patient Consultant Sarah Jungnickel	civil society, research communities	EHN	Sep 2023
Biotech Europe 2023 conference @ Basel Switzerland	attendance and discussions with stakeholders	business, public sector, regulators, startups,	ONTO	Oct 2023
Dataweek BDVA	attendance and discussion with policy makers and representatives of other projects	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities	ONTO	June 2023
RANLP 2023	attendance and discussions with other NLP experts,	business, startups, research communities	ONTO	Sep 2023

⁵⁶ <https://www.swissbiotech.org/listing/biotechx-europe-2023/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.ontotext.com/company/event/biotechx-europe-2023/>

Commun. activity name	Description	Target Audience	Lead partner	When
ISWC 2023	attendance and discussions with semantic technology experts	business, startups, research communities	ONTO	Nov 2023
Infoday Horizon Europe 2023 in Sofia	attendance and discussions with policy makers and other projects	business, public sector, regulators, startups, research communities	ONTO	Sep 2023

3 Conclusion

During the M1-M18 period, the AIDAVA consortium has defined and employed a dissemination, exploitation and communication strategy, described in the PDEC (D6.2). Towards achieving its objectives, a suitable project identity and accompanying digital and physical materials were introduced in the D6.4 *AIDAVA Communication Toolkit*.

The project's website, described in D6.1 *Public Project Website*, and introductory video, corresponding to D6.5 *Audio-visual material*, are communicated in accordance with the guidelines outlined in PDEC and the Communication Toolkit. The consortium members have also diligently followed those guidelines in other AIDAVA dissemination and communication activities, both on digital and physical platforms.

As of February 2024, the consortium is on course towards meeting the objectives set out in the PDEC, which are continuously monitored and updated both via regular meetings of the project's Communication Committee, as well as via updates of the PDEC in the form of deliverables D6.6 *Update of the PDEC in official report 1*, D6.9 *Update of the PDEC in official report 2*, and D6.12 *Update of the PDEC in official report 3*, due in M18, M36, and M48, respectively.

Appendix 1 List of communication activities

Social media networks

X

aidava_project @aidava_project · Dec 4, 2023

Meet our partners: Excited to start our #interview series with Kerli Norak from North Estonia Medical Centre. Read more about Kerli's role and find out what she values most in working in international collaboration projects. Read the interview here: aidava.eu/about/intervie...

0:04 / 0:10

aidava_project reposted **The Augmented Pathologist** @AugPath · Dec 1, 2023

@aidava_project project member meeting at the @iHD_HealthData conference in #Gent - discussing #DataQuality and #Trustworthiness of #HealthData

#BuildingTrustinHealthData #2023 #iHD #annualconference #dataquality

aidava_project reposted **Digital Health Uptake (DHU)** @DHUptake · Dec 1, 2023

Replying to @DHUptake and @iHD_HealthData

- 1 Unify Patients' Records: @1patientrecord
- 2 Framework for Health Apps: @Label2E
- 3 Digital Support and Personalized Care: @adlife_project
- 4 Cardiovascular Healthcare Improvement: @aidava_project
- 5 Remote Monitoring: Bytefiles

Thanks to @iHD_HealthData for having us!

empirica and 7 others

aidava_project reposted **Ontotext** @ontotext · Nov 28, 2023

We recently hosted the @aidava_project ontology workshop focused on representing longitudinal #healthrecords in the form of a Personal Health #KnowledgeGraph.

AIDAVA is a @HorizonEU project that aims to revolutionize personal health #datamanagement hubs.la/Q02b8BQR0

aidava_project @aidava_project · Nov 22, 2023

#AI-powered Solutions to #PersonalizedHealthcare Using #KnowledgeGraphs: Great #Interview with our project coordinator @Celebi_Remzi_. Have a read!

Ontotext @ontotext · Nov 22, 2023

"Transparent consent processes empower individuals to make informed decisions about how their data is used & shared for research & healthcare improvement."

...@aidava_project is focused on empowerment through better ... [Show more](#)

aidava_project reposted **Ontotext** @ontotext · Nov 13, 2023

Join us for the third edition of the Ontotext's #KnowledgeGraph Forum which starts tomorrow!

FREE Registration: hubs.la/Q028Fcpv0

Expect a deep dive into our #semantictchnology ecosystem w/ 40+ speakers & 30+ sessions.

#linkeddata #textanalytics #KGF23 #LLM #SPARQL

aidava_project reposted

EOSC4Cancer @EOSC4Cancer · Aug 11, 2023
 #Cancer patients, survivors and carers can interact with their health data in many ways. What technologies are you using now – and what do you expect to use in the future? Take @aidava_project's survey and contribute to their research!

aidava_project @aidava_project · Jul 17, 2023
 Please support our #research and answer this short #questionnaire on your interaction with your #personalhealthdata – it will take less than 5 minutes. #PHD #PHR. The survey is available in English, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Hungarian, Romania.
 redcap.medunigraz.at/surveys/?s=YLM...

AIDAVA

ONLINE SURVEY

What changes do you expect to see in the next 5 years in how you interact with your personal health information?

SUPPORT OUR RESEARCH

2 3 277

aidava_project @aidava_project · Jul 17, 2023

Please support our #research and answer this short #questionnaire on your interaction with your #personalhealthdata – it will take less than 5 minutes. #PHD #PHR. The survey is available in English, Dutch, Estonian, French, German, Hungarian, Romania.
 redcap.medunigraz.at/surveys/?s=YLM...

AIDAVA

ONLINE SURVEY

What changes do you expect to see in the next 5 years in how you interact with your personal health information?

SUPPORT OUR RESEARCH

1 7 6 1.3K

aidava_project reposted

ECPC @cancereu · Sep 20, 2023
 Join us in building an AI-powered virtual assistant! @aidava_project needs your input to enhance personal health records.
 Fill out our Health & Digital Literacy Questionnaire to help assess user literacy levels.
 Contribute now: redcap.link/tvtrqc4h #FAIRdata

AIDAVA Funded by the European Union

AIDAVA Health And Digital Literacy

3 5 163

aidava_project reposted

The Augmented Pathologist @AugPath · Jun 12, 2023
 having a productive 2-days workshop for the @aidava_project for #integration, #deployment and #humaninteraction of the prototype in Vienna with our colleagues from @MaastrichtU @ontotext @Averbis @MedUniGraz

#AIDAVA #HealthcareInnovation #VirtualAssistant #Workshop #Vienna

Med Uni Graz and 4 others

1 7 167

aidava_project reposted

The Augmented Pathologist @AugPath · Jun 13, 2023
 productive discussions about #reference #ontologies and #annotation during our @aidava_project workshop in sunny #Vienna

#AIDAVA #healthresearch #ontologie #virtualassistant #workshop #Vienna

SBA Research – Science for better security and 4 others

1 5 139

aidava_project reposted

Ontotext @ontotext · Jun 6, 2023
 What is the Personal Health #KnowledgeGraph (PHKG) & why is it important?

An interview w/ Isabelle de Zegher, clinical co-coordinator for @aidava_project discussing the added value that #semantictchnologies KGs bring to the Healthcare domain.

Semantic Technologies and Knowledge Graphs in Healthcare: An Interview with...

From ontotext.com

1 4 219

LinkedIn

Interviews with members of the consortium

AIDAVA
126 followers
2mo

Meet our partners: Excited to start of our [#Interview](#) series with Kerli N. from North Estonia Medical Centre. Read more about Kerli's role in the project and find out what she values most in working in international collaborati ...see more

AIDAVA
Automate Curation and Publishing of Personal Health Data Through Artificial Intelligence

12

AIDAVA
126 followers
2mo

New Interview Alert! Meet [Kris Collins](#) from [Averbis GmbH](#), deputy team leader tasked with creating novel deep learning and machine learning tools to extract relevant clinical information from unstructured text. Find out! ...see more

AIDAVA
Automate Curation and Publishing of Personal Health Data Through Artificial Intelligence

30

AIDAVA
126 followers
2w

We are happy to introduce [Stefan Schulz](#) from [Averbis GmbH](#). Stefan is particularly tasked with the inclusion of the [Averbis GmbH](#) tools into the text annotation [#AIDAVA](#) workflow in terms of pre-annotation. Read the ...see more

AIDAVA
Automate Curation and Publishing of Personal Health Data Through Artificial Intelligence

11

AIDAVA reposted this

Ontotext
7,582 followers
8mo

What is the Personal Health [#KnowledgeGraph](#) (PHKG) & why is it important?

An interview w/ [Isabelle de Zegher](#), clinical co-coordinator for [AIDAVA](#) discussing the added value that [#semantictechnologies](#) & [#knowledgegraphs](#) bring to key stakeholders in the Healthcare domain. <https://hubs.ly/Q015skhd0>

Semantic Technologies and Knowledge Graphs in Healthcare: An Interview with Isabelle de Zegher
ontotext.com

18

Workshops, General assemblies & other consortium gatherings

AIDAVA reposted this

Ontotext
7,582 Followers
2mo

We recently hosted the **AIDAVA** ontology workshop which discussed how to represent personal longitudinal health records in the form of a Personal Health **#KnowledgeGraph**.

The project is one of the Horizon EU projects that aims to revolutionize personal health **#datamanagement** by leveraging **#AI** for data curation, emphasizing patient control & interoperability.

Learn more <https://hubs.la/Q02b8NNm0>

42 · 1 Comment

AIDAVA reposted this

Gabrijela Radić
Project Manager
4mo · Edited

AIDAVA General Assembly Meeting - Day 2 Wrap-up
As the second day of the **#AIDAVA** General Assembly comes to a close, we're taking a moment to reflect on the **#communication** and **#dissemination** aspects of **#AIDAVA**.

Today's agenda was packed with knowledge sharing and strategic planning. Our member presentations show the project achievements, highlighting the dedication and hard work that continues to propel AIDAVA forward. Special thanks to our presenters for their invaluable insights and to all participants for their active engagement and thoughtful queries. Day 3 promises even more enriching content and discussions. Let's gear up for another day of progress, collaboration, and knowledge exchange!

#AIDAVA #GA2023 #AssemblyMeeting #AI #healthdata #Day2WrapUp
EURICE – European Research and Project Office GmbH

29

AIDAVA
126 followers
4mo · Edited

A big thank you to our hosts **Medizinische Universität Graz** and all the amazing participants for having us. 🙌 It's truly inspiring to see how we are all coming together to make a difference.

At the heart of our discussions was the development of a digital solution for more efficient curation of personal health data. 🏡 This initiative is not just about technology; it's about transforming the way we approach healthcare for the benefit of patients and clinical researchers. 🏥👩‍⚕️

I can't wait to hear updates from all the different groups within **#AIDAVA** as we continue to collaborate and innovate in the realm of **#PHD**. Let's keep pushing the boundaries and working towards a healthier future! 🏡🏠

#HealthTech #Innovation #Collaboration #DigitalHealth
#FutureOfHealthcare #AIDAVACommunity

Isabelle de Zegher Remzi Celebi Michel Dumontier Ontotext Egnosis Averbis GmbH IHD KU Leuven European Cancer Patient Coalition Maastricht University Institute of Data Science MIDATA

32 · 1 Comment

Participation in scientific, industry and other conferences and events

AIDAVA reposted this

Egnosis
506 Followers
6mo · Edited

Smart Ideas for smart hospitals

Last week we were in [#Tusvanyos](#), having been invited to discuss [#healthcareinnovation](#) and [#digitalization](#) within the Miercurea Ciuc Emergency Hospital and opportunities on its road to evolving into a smart hospital. Institution managers, chief medical officers and hospital directors presented the hospital's digitalization level, recent progress and digitization trends, shaping the future smart hospital in Miercurea Ciuc. [Béla Bihari](#) was sharing [Egnosis'](#) experience in looking for digitization solutions for the development of various fields of medicine with the best researchers of Western Europe in several transnational projects, such as [FeatureCloud](#), [REPO4EU](#), [AIDAVA](#) or [Microb-AI-ome](#).

This first gathering aimed to resonate with the language of [#Innovation](#), and we are excitedly looking forward to seeing and making the ideas come to life!

19

Other posts on LinkedIn

AIDAVA reposted this

European Cancer Patient Coalition
4,926 Followers
4mo

Would you like to contribute to the development of a virtual assistant powered by AI? We need your help! 🙌

AIDAVA is building a data cleaning machine that can help patients maintain a HIGH-QUALITY personal health record.

📄 Take a moment to fill out this Health & Digital Literacy Questionnaire. Your input will help on the assessment of the right literacy levels of AIDAVA users! 📄

Do you want to know more about #AIDAVA project? 📄 <https://www.aidava.eu/>

🔗 Click here to fill the form: [#FAIRdata](https://lnkd.in/e6MQrmeX)

AIDAVA Health And Digital Literacy

<https://redcap.link/1vtrqc4h>
redcap.medunigraz.at

👍 9

AIDAVA
126 Followers
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Today is **#InternationalDayofWomenandGirlsInScience** – an annual celebration of the achievements and contributions of women and girls in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (**#STEM**). 📄 📄

At **#AIDAVA**, we're privileged to have an exceptional team of women working towards a quantum leap in automating the curation and publication of **#personalhealthdata** by orchestrating multiple Artificial Intelligence (**#AI**)-based solutions.

INTERNATIONAL DAY OF WOMEN & GIRLS IN SCIENCE

AIDAVA

👍❤️📄 27